

Synthesis of Quaternary Salts of Ammonia from Phenols and their Plant Growth Retardant Activity

M. L. SHARMA*, K. K. TALWAR and REEMA DUGGAL

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 28 January 1997, revised 21 October 1997, accepted 24 November 1997

Different phenols, viz. β -naphthol, *p*-chlorophenol, *p*-cresol and *m*-nitrophenol have been converted into (3-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloxy) derivatives (4a-d) through the formation of glycidyl ethers (2a-d and 3a-d). *m*-Nitrophenol and *p*-chlorophenol have been converted to 2-aryloxy-*N,N*-diethylaminoethanes (8e,f) through the formation of bromoethers (7e,f). 1,3-Bis(2-diethylaminoethoxy)benzene (12) has been prepared from resorcinol. The tertiary amines (4a-d, 8e,f and 12) are then quaternized with citronellyl bromide and tested as plant growth retardants.

We reported earlier¹ that the quaternary salts of ammonia prepared from phenol, salicylaldehyde and α -naphthol through the formation of glycidyl ethers, have plant-growth retardant effect on the germination and seedling growth of turnip seeds (*Brassica rapa* L.) but no structure-activity relationship could be established. Here we presents the synthesis and plant - growth retardant activities of four quaternary salts of ammonia, prepared from β -naphthol, *p*-chlorophenol, *p*-methoxyphenol and *m*-nitrophenol through the formation of glycidyl ethers, and three from *m*-nitrophenol, *p*-chlorophenol and resorcinol prepared through the formation of ethyl ethers. These compounds may be useful in agriculture for bud and seed dormancy and preventing growth of wide range of pathogens.

β -Naphthol, *p*-chlorophenol, *p*-methoxyphenol and *m*-nitrophenol separately on treatment with epichlorohydrin in presence of 7% aq. KOH produced a mixture of 2,3-epoxypropyloxy (2a-d)² and 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyloxy (3a-d)³ derivatives. This mixture was then refluxed with diethylamine to produce 3-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloxy derivatives (4a-d) (Chart 1).

In order to prepare quaternary salts through the formation of ethyl ethers, *m*-nitrophenol and *p*-chlorophenol were separately treated with dibromoethane in the presence of aq. NaOH to produce 2-(3-nitrophenoxy)bromoethane (7e) and 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)bromoethane (7f) respectively. The bromides (7e,f) were then converted to the corresponding tertiary amines (8e,f) by refluxing with anhydrous K₂CO₃ in acetone⁴. 1,3-Bis(2-diethylaminoethoxy)benzene (12) was similarly prepared from resorcinol (Chart 2).

The tertiary amines (4a-d, 8e,f, 12) were then refluxed with citronellyl bromide in dry acetone⁵ to give the quaternary salts (5a-d, 9e,f, 13).

Biological activity⁶ : To test the biological activity of these compounds, their effects on the germination and seedling growth of turnip seeds (Table 1) and rooting of hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata* (Table 2) were studied. All the compounds inhibited germination and seedling growth

Chart 1

TABLE 1-PLANT GROWTH RETARDANT ACTIVITY OF QUATERNARY SALTS OF AMMONIA

Compd.	Percent germination of seedings at various concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)				Average length (in cm) of seedings at various concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)			
	10	25	50	100	10	25	50	100
5a	87	66	36	8	2.70	1.99	0.80	0.27
5b	86	76	67	26	3.05	2.36	2.32	1.65
5c	78	67	35	7	4.25	3.11	1.31	0.48
5d	82	71	42	26	2.21	1.94	1.17	0.56
9e	77	64	51	30	3.25	2.45	1.92	0.72
9f	90	73	70	46	3.23	2.46	1.80	1.70
13	83	67	41	32	3.58	2.20	1.84	1.75
CD at 5% (compound A)					=	0.03	.001	
CD at 5% (concentration) B					=	0.02	.001	
CD at 5% (compound \times concentration) A \times B =					0.06	.002		
(CD = Critical difference)								
ABA ($5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)						16	0.34 cm	
Water						100	1.77 cm	

of turnip seeds. The magnitude of inhibition increased with increase in the concentration of the compounds. The inhibitory effect on the germination of turnip seeds and on seedling growth of compounds 5a and 5c was greater at higher concentration than that of abscisic acid (ABA) at $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. This suggests that plant growth inhibitory effect of the molecules of the type 5 can be increased by introducing such substituents in the benzene ring that can enhance the

electron density of the ring, whereas the molecules in which benzene ring is substituted with electron-withdrawing groups (Cl, NO₂) are comparatively less effective. On the other hand, compounds **5a**, **5d** and **9e** having electron-withdrawing groups (Cl and NO₂) on the benzene ring showed plant growth inhibitory effect at 20 μg ml⁻¹ better than that of ABA at 5 μg ml⁻¹ on rooting of hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata*. This suggests that the groups which decrease the electron density of the benzene ring enhance the plant growth inhibitory effect of the quaternary salts of ammonia on the induction of rooting.

TABLE 2—PLANT GROWTH RETARDANT ACTIVITY OF QUATERNARY SALTS OF AMMONIA

Compd. no.	No. of roots (average) at different concentrations (μg ml ⁻¹)			
	5	10	15	20
5a	8.3	8.0	5.42	3.0
5b	5.33	5.0	4.1	1.0
5c	5.62	5.2	3.5	2.2
5d	5.1	2.4	1.8	1.0
9e	3.3	2.4	1.0	0.2
9f	5.0	3.5	2.7	1.8
13	4.1	3.8	2.4	1.9
CD at 5% (compound) A				= 0.86
CD at 5% (concentration) B				= 0.49
CD at 5% (compound × concentration) A × B				= 1.30
ABA control	1.6 ± 0.14			
Water (control)	4.25 ± 0.11			

Experimental

B.ps. are uncorrected, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃/CCl₄) were recorded on a EM-390/360 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer. The homogeneity of compounds was

routinely checked on silica gel tlc plates.

2-(3-Diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloxy)naphthalene (4a): To a stirred solution of β-naphthol (1.4 g, 9.7 mmol) in aqueous KOH (7%, 10 ml), epichlorohydrin (1 ml) was added dropwise at 10–15° during 0.5 h. The stirring was continued for 36 h at room temperature. The separated oil was extracted with benzene (3 × 50 ml) and the combined extract was washed with aqueous NaOH solution (10%) and water. Removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation afforded a thick material, whose tlc showed two spots. This was used as such in the next step.

A mixture of the above material and diethylamine (5 ml) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (20 ml) for 4 h, then cooled and alcohol was distilled off. The resulting oil was distilled under reduced pressure to give **4a** (2.1 g, 82%), b.p. 225–28°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 74.61; H, 8.57; N, 5.25. C₁₇H₂₃O₂N calcd. for : C, 74.73; H, 8.42; N, 5.13%); ν_{max} (neat) 3420 cm⁻¹(OH); δ 1.06 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.53–2.8 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₃), 3.1 (1H, s, CHOH), 4.0–4.4 (3H, m, OCH₂CHOH), 7.1–7.7 (7H, m, ArH).

Compounds **4b–d** were prepared similarly from *p*-chlorophenol, *p*-methoxyphenol and *m*-nitrophenol respectively : **4b** (1.8 g, 84%), b.p. 180–84°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 60.72; H, 7.68; N, 5.39. C₁₃H₂₁O₂N calcd. for : C, 60.58; H, 7.77; N, 5.44%); ν_{max} (neat) 3420 cm⁻¹(OH); δ 1.03 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.4–2.8 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₃), 3.8–4.2 (4H, m, OCH₂CHOH), 6.9–7.3 (7H, ArH); **4c** (2.2 g, 90%), b.p. 190–93°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 66.31; H, 9.01; N, 5.62. C₁₄H₂₃O₃N calcd. for : C, 66.40; H, 9.09; N, 5.53%); ν_{max} (neat) 3430 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 1.04 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.7–3.1 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.45–3.75 (3H, m, OCH₂OH), 4.25 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.0–7.33 (4H, ArH); **4d** (2.18 g, 84%); b.p. 170–75°/5–6 mm (Found : C, 58.29; H, 7.41; N, 10.56. C₁₃H₂₀O₄N₂ calcd. for : C, 58.21; H, 7.46; N, 10.45%); ν_{max} (neat) 3430 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 1.03 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₃), 2.35–2.7 (6H, m, CH₂N-(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.7–3.95 (3H, m, OCH₂CHOH), 4.29 (1H, s, OH), 6.8–7.4 (4H, m, ArH).

N,N-Diethyl-1-(3-nitrophenoxy)aminoethane (8e): To a mixture of *m*-nitrophenol (4 g, 28.8 mmol) and ethylene bromide (7.5 g, 40 mmol), a solution of NaOH (1 g, in 10 ml of water) was added dropwise over a period of 15 min. It was refluxed with stirring for 6 h at 120°. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with benzene (3 × 25 ml). The combined extract was washed successively with 2*N* NaOH and water. Solvent was then distilled off from the dried extract (over Na₂SO₄) to give the bromide **7e**.

A mixture of the bromide (**7e**, 3.5 g, 14.2 mmol), diethylamine (1.4 g, 28.4 mmol), potassium carbonate (2 g, 15 mmol) and acetone (50 ml) was refluxed with stirring at 60° for 6 h. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and most of the acetone was removed by distillation. Water (15 ml) was then added and the solution was extracted with ether. Removal of the solvent from the dried extract (over Na₂SO₄) followed by vacuum distillation afforded the

NOTE

amine **8e** (2.9 g, 86%), b.p. 175–80°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 60.41; H, 7.48; N, 11.87. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3N_2$ calcd. for : C, 60.50; H, 7.50; N, 11.76%); δ 1.03 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 2.43–2.9 (6H, m, $CH_2N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 3.7 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 6.8–7.4 (4H, m, ArH).

Similarly, the tertiary amines (**8f**, **12**) were prepared from *p*-chlorophenol (**6f**) and resorcinol (**10**) respectively : **8f** (2.7 g, 84%), b.p. 180–83°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 63.18; H, 7.98; N, 6.03. $C_{12}H_{18}ONCl$ calcd. for : C, 63.30; H, 7.91; N, 6.15%); δ 1.06 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 2.7–3.1 (6H, m, $CH_2N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, t, OCH_2), 6.8–7.4 (4H, m, ArH); **12** (4g, 91%), b.p. 190–95°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 70.28; H, 10.26; N, 9.21. $C_{18}H_{32}O_2N_2$ calcd. for : C, 70.13; H, 10.39; N, 9.09%); δ 1.13 (12H, t, J 7 Hz, $2 \times N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 2.5–3.0 (12H, m, $2 \times CH_2N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 3.6 (4H, t, J 7 Hz, $2 \times ArOCH_2$), 6.6–7.35 (4H, m, ArH).

Evaluation of plant growth retardant activities. To test the germination and seedling growth study, turnip seeds (*Brassica rapa* var. L1, 50) in three replications were placed on filter paper (Whatman no. 42) laid on the bottom of a petri dish of 9 cm diameter to which 5 ml of test solutions of different concentrations (10, 25, 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of the compounds were poured. Each dish was kept at $28 \pm$

1° for 72 h and then the per cent seed germination and seedling lengths were recorded. Separate control treatments with ABA at concentrations (5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and water were also recorded simultaneously. To test growth retarding effect of the salts, hypocotyl cuttings of moongbean (*Vigna radiata* L., 10) were taken in a vial to which 20 ml of test solutions of different concentrations (5, 10, 15 and 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of compounds were poured. Each vial was kept at $28 \pm 1^\circ$ for 7 days and thereafter, the number of roots were recorded. Separate control treatments with ABA at concentrations 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and water were also recorded simultaneously.

References

1. M. L. SHARMA, K. K. TALWAR, and A. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 343.
2. S. D. SAMANT, S. M. GUPTA, and P. A. KULKARNI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 524.
3. J. ZAAGSMA and T. W. NAUTA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, **20**, 527.
4. R. K. MAHAJAN and M. M. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, **16**, 430.
5. W. F. NEWHALL and A. P. PIERINGER, *J. Agric. Food. Chem.*, 1966, **14**, 23.
6. ISTA, International Rules for Seed Testing, *Seed Sci. Tech.*, 1976, **4**, 1.